

Integrating Electronic Circuit Design and Fabrication in a Design Studio: Discussing Hands-on Learning Approach to Engage Undergraduate Students in Ecologically Relevant Design

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Abstract

This paper examines the experience of integrating electronic circuit design and fabrication to support the creation of ecologically relevant design propositions in an undergraduate design studio. The authors describe the implementation of a new curriculum for a nine weeks course, developed as a collaboration between Fablab Shanghai and the Ecology and Cultures Innovation Lab of the College of Design and Innovation at Tongji University. They explain how they used hands-on tutorials and experiential learning activities as instructional methods to teach electronic circuit design to students with no prior knowledge of the subject. The structure of the course is outlined detailing the adoption of short challenges and practical activities that covered the entire process of creating an integrated electronic product, including design, fabrication, programming and debugging. Additionally, the paper details how the technical knowledge was used to support the design research for the studio's brief, which aimed at contributing to new forms of connection between citizens and Nature, fostering the creation of ecological knowledge. In this respect, the authors emphasise the importance of maintaining a continuous interconnection between technical and ecological topics throughout the design process and highlight how the experiences and motivations enabled by this interplay influenced the design decisions of students. Lastly, the paper discusses the outcomes of the studio according to their ecological relevance and the completeness of the integrated product, suggesting that experiential learning could be a methodological asset in projects developing more-than-human design scenarios.

Keywords

Electronic design, experiential learning, ecological knowledge, design education, cross-disciplinarity

1 Introduction

Since 2020 the Fab Lab of the College of Design and Innovation of Tongji University in Shanghai started a collaboration with the newly established Ecology and Cultures Innovation Lab¹, a research centre whose aim is to extend the scope of design from human-centred to life-centred activities. The form of this collaboration took shape within the “Studio 5 Urban Nature and Fabrication” course, the professional course of the third year propaedeutic to the students’ final graduation projects. Professors introduce the

¹ Link to the website of the Ecology and Cultures Innovation Lab. <https://ecology.shanghai-visual.org/web/about-us/>

topics of the courses they intend to offer, allowing students to select a topic based on their personal interests with the opportunity to choose courses from various design majors.

For this first collaboration, Fablab Shanghai provided fabrication and making expertise to the novel pedagogical methodology of the Ecology Lab whose aim is to stimulate and inspire a new design culture that does not create boundaries with the environment but instead explores interconnectedness. Fabrication was used as a way to challenge the established creative practice of third year's students, introducing hands-on activities early in the design process as a way to enhance the connection with Nature through the stimulation of all senses.

While the guidelines of this studio did not require electronic prototyping for the final projects, half of the students decided to include functions supported by an electronic system. Although their knowledge of electronic prototyping and programming was average for the third year's level of a Design College, we noticed that the features introduced by the electronic circuit added little value to the quality and meaning of their design proposition. In some cases, especially when students introduced electronics features only in the making phase of the final project, the layer added by the electronic system actually trivialised the validity of their design process, acting as a disconnecting element of the relationship between humans and Nature.

Reviewing the results of that first experience, we contemplated the possibility of fostering a continuous interconnection between the technical and ecological topics throughout the entire course. By doing so, we could facilitate the emergence of a mutualistic relationship of knowledge generation between both domains.

With those considerations, we conceived a new format for a similar Studio 5 in which the Fab Lab would provide experiential learning activities addressing the technical aspects of designing, fabricating and using electronic circuits, while fostering the generation of human-nature interaction designs.

1.1 Why electronic design?

In the era of IoT, AI, and other "buzzwords" that often dominate the design discourse characterised by a relentless pursuit of technical novelty (often mislabelled as innovation), virtually every product includes some kind of digital system making it "smart". In a design school, students almost take for granted that every design proposal they make should include some kind of sensor that gathers relevant data and utilises them to make something, with little critical reflection of the data process and the nature of the outcomes. In our practice, we observed that digital systems are considered "smart" by definition and often used uncritically, sometimes in the form of technological "black box" that solve problems with little awareness of how they work in reality, how they benefit the project, or whether they are relevant to discover insights.

It's not uncommon to review students' works proposing unspecified sensors that can discern a person's hunger levels or detect odours with remarkable precision. Although anecdotal, these evidences convinced us that a deeper understanding of how electronic devices work would be beneficial in the education of design students who are about to discuss their ideas with engineers, managers, users and investors in their future practice. With this assumption, we selected electronic design as a technical subject for the new Studio 5 course, developing a curriculum that could guide third year's students in understanding how electronic components work, how to design circuits, how to fabricate prototypes from scratch and how to integrate them in the packaging of their design.

1.2 The Nature Brief

This goal was again associated with the Ecology Lab research practice, formulating the specific brief of "Sensing Ecology"; we aimed at creating devices that could enable interactions between humans and aspects of the natural environment, whether in the setting of urban nature or in general regarding ecological systems, and we expected these interactions to support the acquisition of ecological knowledge prior to the proposal of a design intervention.

As opposed to the first experience of "Urban Nature and Fabrication", the first Studio 5 course seeing a collaboration of the Fab Lab and the Ecology and Cultures Innovation Lab, in the newly developed course

“Electronic Design and Fabrication for Designers”, the incorporation of electronic prototyping was meant to be an essential component during the preliminary stages of the design process with electronic devices serving as instrumental tools for the research endeavours that formed the foundation of the design proposition. In the emergent more-than-human design scope, the research tasks that are usually associated with human-centred design methods and tools must be redefined. In fact, while in human-centred design the notion of “empathy” is fairly established and it can be developed throughout the basic methodology of text-based interviews or users’ engagement tools, once we speak of more-than-human, the concept of empathy needs to be translated to agents “who cannot answer interviews”, and therefore it requires a new methodology approach.

In previous publications (Valsecchi and Silli 2021) we discussed how empathy towards nature agents could be triggered by embodied research methods, in which sensorial explorations take the place of more structured language-based tools (whereas textual or visual). When referring to sensorial or bodily exploration we already discussed how fabrication can support if not enhance the possibility to go beyond languages (Silli and Valsecchi 2021): by the techniques of rapid prototyping and the fabrication of research tools, the students can “make while thinking” and this allow a progressive and not-disruptive distancing from human perspectives in the direction of recognizing the agency of natural elements and their interconnectedness. This approach not only benefits the design methodology with research tools that are experimental, tri-dimensional, and speculative, but it also creates a legacy for the concept of empathy (as a core concept of design methodology) as a drive for cross-disciplinary inspiration which is currently very relevant in design education.

2 Literature Review

Introducing an engineering-based subject in the third year’s studio course of a design school is a step in the direction of adopting a cross-disciplinary approach in design education. Despite Donald Norman advocated this concept as a necessary step for the evolution of design education already a decade ago (Norman 2010), Muratovski identifies several challenges that reduce or hinder the chances for this integration of being successful: problems related to a lack of knowledge of other disciplines, divergent standards, different methodological approaches, or even to negative attitudes and prejudices across disciplines (Muratovski 2011). As pointed out by Meyer and Norman (2020), other disciplines like engineering, medicine and business, were successful in overcoming these challenges and updating their education systems, while design is still behind pursuing this goal. For example, in engineering based subjects such as electronic design, the challenges posed by the introduction of cross-disciplinarity in the education system have been overcome in some cases with the adoption of solutions that rely on the applied learning approach peculiar to a design context. As Bingham explains: *“These attributes highlighted a significant opportunity to improve the current teaching and learning of engineering-based subjects through the introduction of applied learning in a PBL environment. To achieve this, it was decided to incorporate the design context directly into the engineering-based curricular utilising a design project vehicle. Instead of relying almost exclusively on the students’ ability to contextualise and transfer engineering-based knowledge into design practice, this approach would help formalise and reinforce this key learning process”* (Bingham et al. 2013, page 171).

While the application of design methodologies to other disciplines has proven itself both valuable and feasible, design education is still struggling with successfully incorporating elements of other disciplines that could benefit the learning and formative process of design students (Meyer and Norman 2020). Especially when introducing an engineering based subject such as electronic design to design students (Bingham et al. 2013), certain difficulties arise for the lack of familiarity with the technical vocabulary (Herr 2014) and for the lack of experience in the execution skills needed to deal with more technical disciplines.

While in our school some of the students who are enrolled in the Industrial Design course have the opportunity to use a simplified electronic prototyping system such as Arduino², those coming from Environmental Design and Media & Communication design can be considered neophytes of this skillset. As described by Mellis et al. (2016), in the last decades, efforts to involve individuals without professional expertise in electronics have often relied on toolkits or breadboards as accessible means of engagement. Several electronic toolkits provide collections of high-level electronic modules that neophytes can easily combine in different configurations. With the modules in a toolkit, electronic functionalities can be introduced early in the design phase of a project, to create functional prototypes without the need to understand “how” the components work or “why” they are made in a certain way (Lee et al. 2004). Other prototyping tools, like the Arduino development system, involve the use of low-level electronic components and a breadboard, but the list of the electronic components to use and the instructions on how to assemble the circuit are bound to the programming code that the user wants to upload on the development board. As described by Greenberg and Fitchett (2001), the motivation for developing easy to use electronic prototyping toolkits was to avoid the inconvenience of choosing and sourcing thousands of different components, dealing with different networking protocols, managing wire connections and programming embedded microcontrollers. Mellis argues that, “*by avoiding (such challenges), people miss a valuable learning and making opportunity*” (Mellis et al. 2016, page 1272). While simplified toolkits allow users to focus on the design process to create early functional prototypes, they are not a valuable resource for producing knowledge in electronic design and they don’t allow the learner to make sense of the subject.

Mellis’ proposed solution to the challenge of engaging neophytes in electronic prototyping was based on personal fabrication, an approach that “*offers a path for the amateur to create robust, repeatable prototypes of electronic devices*” and that “*brings individuals closer to world of commercial electronic products*” (Mellis et al. 2016, pages 1278-1279). A parallel between personal fabrication and personal computing was discussed by Neil Gershenfeld (2012) in relation to the experience of the class called “How to make (Almost) Anything” at MIT’S Center for Bits and Atoms. The class and its derivative, Fab Academy (Troxler 2016), supported by the Fab Lab, a facility that is equipped with digital fabrication tools, is the example of a higher-education curriculum which successfully allows students with heterogeneous background to master electronic design, production and programming in a short amount of time. The Fab Lab’s teaching and learning environment employs multiple styles of engagement, including hard (top-down) and soft (bottom-up) approaches (Turkle and Papert 1992), embracing constructivist methods that support learners in building their own skills (Glaserfeld 1995). Within the physical space of the Fab Lab, students are exposed to technological resources, fabrication materials, tools and equipment, an environment designed to stimulate and empower them to construct their own learning path (Angeli et al. 2019), through the quick availability and ease of access of such training material (Mikhak et al. 2002).

The literature analysis suggests that, to evolve, design education shall employ cross-disciplinarity not as an abstract concept but as a practice-based challenge. The question therefore becomes “How to do this?”: in line with the findings emerged from the literature review, this paper discusses a curriculum that leverages on personal fabrication to deliver technical knowledge in a design context. While we believe this approach is valuable regardless of the particularity of the design brief to which it is applied, by leveraging on the research questions advanced by the Ecology and Cultures Innovation Lab, we propose that a shift from human-centred to more-than-human design would constitute a valuable space for students to radically change not only how they work on projects, but also which kind of projects they work on (Camocini and Vergani 2021).

3 Methodology

The development of our curriculum started by conceiving a framework that could combine the technical elements of electronic design with the principles of design practice familiar to the students, within the

² Link to the official website, <http://www.arduino.cc>

scope established by the “Sensing Ecology” design brief. We identified a simple but compelling analogy between the input and output structure of electronic systems and the cause-and-effect relationship of ecological systems and we hypothesised that referring to this analogy throughout the course would have been helpful to:

- Limit the number of electronic design’s topics to address and reduce the amount of technical knowledge necessary to fabricate basic but solid printed circuit boards (PCB).
- Provide a frame to navigate the complexity of ecological systems.
- Lay down a scaffolding to build empathy with pluriversal relationships through the application of electronic devices.

Based on this input-output/cause-effect framework, the curriculum had to keep into account several other factors such as the students’ level of familiarity with electronic based activities, the number of students enrolled and the availability and accessibility of an adequate amount of equipment and materials. We set the maximum number of students to enrol to 8 per semester, estimating this number as the limit to keep the cost of materials within budget and maintaining the machine-use time amount to optimal levels for every student. We circulated a simple questionnaire among the enrolled students to figure out their perceived skill level on various topics such as prototyping circuits with Arduino and toolkit modules, embedded programming and manual fabrication skills. With a cohort including students from industrial design, media and communication design and environmental design, the result indicated generally average or below average levels for each skill. Therefore, we decided to outline a curriculum dedicated to students with no prior technical skills.

With a schedule of 4 hours per day, 2 days a week and 9 weeks in total, we divided the course into 9 units corresponding to the 9 weeks. Additionally, we adopted the micro-challenge model described by Gerodimou et al. (2022) to design three challenges with increasing levels of complexity to be completed at three separate stages of the course.

3.1 One day challenge

The first challenge, to be completed in one day, was to assemble a so-called “Arduino on a breadboard”³, a simple circuit including an ATmega328 microcontroller (an extremely common chip with extensive documentation) and a set of low-level electronic components to control and enable various functions of the chip. This was conceived as an “ice breaking” activity to familiarise with various electronic components and procedures and assemble a fully functional prototyping board similar to the widely used Arduino Uno. This board was subsequently employed to run the first tests and exercises, connecting input and output devices, exchange data with the computer through serial communication and as a reference for students to design their own circuit with an electronic design software (cf. Figure 1).

3.2 One week challenge

The second challenge, to be completed in one week, was to manufacture a PCB board designed by the students using the tools in the Fab Lab. With a series of lectures and tutorials the students learned how to use Eagle, a free access electronic design software⁴, export the files and generate a CAM code to operate a desktop sized CNC precision milling machine (Roland SRM20). The board, milled out of FR1 copper-plated phenolic paper material was then polished and the selected electronic components soldered to the board. The last task was to upload the first code to the microcontroller to test the correct functionality of the PCB (cf. Figure 2).

³ Link to the tutorial, <https://docs.arduino.cc/hacking/hardware/building-an-arduino-on-a-breadboard>

⁴ Link to the distributor’s page, <https://www.autodesk.com/products/eagle>

3.3 One month challenge

The last challenge, to be completed in one month, was dedicated to the design and fabrication of the final project, an electronic device that would allow or facilitate new relationships between citizens and Nature. The PCB needed to be redesigned to allow it to be fabricated by a factory with industrial grade standards, and the other components of the device were developed and manufactured by the students with digital fabrication equipment inside the Fab Lab (cf. Figure 3).

Figure 1: “Arduino on a Breadboard”.

Figure 2: CNC-milled PCB by student Gao Peizhong.

Figure 3: Factory-made PCB, design by student Gao Shihan.

Alongside the three challenges, we included a series of learning and experiencing activities and short hands-on workshops throughout the course (cf. Table 1). These activities were designed to deliver learning

points on electronic design and simultaneously deepen the focus on ecology related matters, while sticking to the methodology of a design process framework. The space where these activities took place, with the exception of the Campus' garden exploration, was the Fab Lab, which served as the classroom for the whole course. Studio courses are normally based in generic classrooms of the College of Design, but hosting the course inside the Fab Lab was a deliberate decision to leverage on the "sandbox culture" that is directly inherited by the Fab Lab birthplace, MIT's Media Lab (Koskinen et al. 2012). We believed that immersing ourselves in a space filled with wires, components, tools, old projects and materials of all sorts, and being this a place of continuous changes, would have been beneficial to feed the hands-on approach adopted by our curriculum.

3.4 Hand-sketching components

With the "Arduino on a breadboard" exercise, students are introduced to all the basic electronic components which they will use throughout the whole course. They are:

- 1, Resistor; 2, Capacitor; 3, LED diode; 4, Voltage Regulator; 5, Crystal; 6, Microcontroller; 7, USB-Serial Pin Headers connector.

The exercise we proposed was to hand-draw a sketch that resembled the style of naturalistic illustration. We first projected a few illustrations of natural elements, to point at some notable elements such as the use of section, exploded or magnified views or the presence of short descriptive text with pointing arrows. This exercise allowed the students to research the way components are made and what they are used for and on the following day each student was asked to elaborate their drawing and prepare a short lecture explaining their findings to the rest of the class, in a flipped classroom fashion.

Table 1: Summary of the experiential activities and their relation to the technology, ecology and design aspects.

	Activity	Technology	Ecology	Design
1	Hand-sketching components	How components are made and how they work	Nature inspired illustration	Desktop research
2	Input devices try-out	Data collection and access	Observe natural phenomena in greater details	Interview
3	Campus' garden exploration		Deep experience, sensorial engagement, change of scale	Field research
4	Output devices try-out	Data usage, actuators control, power management	Analysis and representation of cause-effect relationship in ecological systems	Interpretation and insights definition
5	Very Rapid prototyping	Circuits prototyping and programming	Hands-on sensorial engagement	Ideation

3.5 Input devices try-out

This workshop introduced data collection with digital and analog input devices. After a demonstration of a selection of sensors, we asked students to pick one sensor from a collection and try it out with their prototyping breadboard and a suitable program. Each student repeated the exercise with several sensors

and at the end they were asked to reflect on the physical phenomenon at the root of the sensor's functionality.

3.6 Campus' garden exploration

This activity was borrowed from a previous experience (Valsecchi and Silli 2021) carried out in the first studio course of the Ecology and Cultures Innovation Lab. Similar to field research, the exploration of a urban nature setting such as the garden of Tongji University's campus, was carried out to engage the students in the deep observation of natural elements, performing a sort of interview to entities who cannot respond verbally and producing a report in the form of sketches, maps or annotated photos. Students were advised to allow a "change of scale", adopting alternative strategies such as shutting down their senses and focusing on one sense in succession, use the sense of sight in unusual ways such as lying down on the ground or observing tiny details with a magnifying glass which was given to them. We encouraged students to look at relationships between elements rather than single entities.

3.7 Output devices try-out

Similar to the input devices try out activity, a collection of actuators was available for multiple tests. This time, the students were asked to recall their exploration of the natural environment and encouraged to associate the previously observed relationships of cause and effect with a technological system of input and output. To control the actuator, they must use input data gathered by a sensor they were already familiar with, or collect new data exploring new input devices. The resulting electronic circuits were then used to draw an analogy with an ecological relationship.

3.8 Very Rapid prototyping

This activity was based on a workshop employed in a previous experience (Silli and Valsecchi 2021) of the Ecology and Cultures Innovation Lab in which a prototyping exercise is performed in a very short amount of time with a limited set of materials and tools. The activity took place at a stage in which the students had already developed a working version of their electronic circuit. During this "very rapid prototyping" session, the students were asked to build the basic shape of their device in two hours, using simple materials found in the Fab Lab such as cardboard, paper, scrap wood, rubber bands, straws and various waste materials collected from the garbage bin such as paper cups and single-use cutleries. At this point the students only had a rough idea of what their device will look like and what it will make, so the main requirement was to "just make" whatever they felt was right, to have something usable and testable at the end of the following two hours. This exercise proved extremely useful for understanding sizes, scales, usability and ultimately producing a first platform to define which specific electronic components to use, how to manage power supplies and gather more information about the interaction with the environment that couldn't otherwise be anticipated (cf. Figure 4).

Figure 4: Prototype realised with materials found in the Fab Lab being tested for usability.

It also clarified to the students the meaning of “smartness” in relationship with integrated products: while the electronic system introduces necessary functionalities to a product, it cannot be seen only as a bundle to wrap around a packaging. The careful consideration of how each part of the product is made and works in concert with the others is crucial to achieve a solid, viable and reproducible integrated result. We believe this to be a very important concept that connects technology to the ecological paradigm, and highlights the understanding of systems as organisms, where both the design of the single parts and the design of the whole are strictly related and need to be experimented and integrated.

To keep track of the students’ work more conveniently, we provided a personal storage space to each student on the Fab Lab’s online repository that they had to use to document their advancements on the three challenges and five activities. We employed Wikifactory⁵, a hardware-oriented collaborative manufacturing platform that was already well integrated with the Fab Lab ecosystem.

4 Studio outcomes

Over the course of two semesters, the course produced 15 final projects and here we present 6 of the most representative students’ works, highlighting significant elements of the design process. It’s possible to divide them into two categories derived from the functions enabled by the electronic system and the quality of the human-nature interaction promoted by the devices.

4.1 New Senses

The first category includes those devices that introduce new senses for humans to interact with Nature, borrowed from living organisms. They use electronic sensors to detect physical phenomena and translate the data they gathered in a way that is intelligible by humans with their five senses.

“Percuino” is a headband designed by Gao Peizhong that allows the wearer to experience the peculiar way Snakes, Frogs and Turtles interact with the environment. The PCB on the forehead features three detachable and interchangeable modules each enabling an innovative way of sensing the environment: the “snake module” utilise an infrared temperature sensor to detect the presence of living beings, the “frog module” has a laser motion sensor to detect their motion and the “turtle module” mounts a compass sensor to detect one’s position relative to the magnetic south; lastly, the actuator is a vibration motor that can stimulate the back of the wearer’s head at increasing intensity. In his records, Gao Peizhong reports that during the exploration of the campus his attention was engaged by a snail that emerged after a rain, which led him to tinker with the rain sensor for a while. Thinking of the relationship between the weather conditions and the animal’s behaviour inspired his work (cf. Figure 5).

For his final project titled “Treelapse”, Gao Shihan was initially inspired by the sick trees in the University’s campus and the realisation that the visible scars of a tree are the result of a slow process happening over what is a very long time in human beings’ terms. While exercising with input devices he noticed the extreme precision of the three-axis accelerometer sensor and he tested if it was possible to use it to detect the slow movements of a tree. The final result is a device mounted with straps on a tree trunk that records the tree’s movements over an extended amount of time and uses the data to draw a timelapse visualisation allowing a person to perceive time not in human terms but from the tree’s perspective (cf. Figure 6).

For student Zhu Ziyi, the inspiration came while studying electronic circuit design and the interferences that different electronic frequencies have on the circuit functions. In his research, he found out that several living beings, including insects, are able to detect naturally occurring electromagnetic fields and that artificially generated ones can be perceived as a sort of “noise” by living organisms. His final project “ElectroMata412”, is a small device able to detect, at a very short range, electromagnetic fields generated by common use electronic appliances such as smartphones. Drawing such a device near the PCB’s antenna

⁵ Link to the repository, <https://wikifactory.com/+fablabo/pcb-for-designers-2022>

changed the behaviour of the motor-operated, insect-like automata created by the student, disrupting its regular movements and allowing the user to detect nearby electromagnetic fields (cf. Figure 7).

4.2 Ecological Communication

The second category we identified includes devices whose aim is to communicate about a relationship of cause and effect present in an ecological system, with an interaction that makes visible something that humans generally overlook or ignore.

“Root for Thought” is a project by Song Yue inspired by the “mycorrhizal network”, a network created by fungal mycelium extending underground, capable of joining individual plant’s roots and connecting them to each other (Pringle 2009). The student’s initial understanding of this fascinating relationship was rather superficial, as she tried to explain it through a human perspective (her first proposal resembled a telephone for fungi and trees to talk to each other). Her work went through several iterations exploring sensors and actuators that helped her to transcend humans’ senses, finally leading her to carry out a change of scale. The device is a custom designed and fabricated electronic circuit controlling a large-scale interactive installation representing the roots of plants. The audience’s point of view is that of a fungus enabling connections between plants by touching their roots (cf. Figure 8).

Student Zhou Qingqing designed “Win(g)nable” an interactive game that tells the story of the migration of aphid colonies from one plant to another. During the exploration, she observed several plants damaged by aphids and found out that when an aphid colony starts to experience over-population, the friction on their bodies caused by being confined in a crowded space stimulates the generation of winged offspring in the females. When resources are depleted, the colony has a chance to survive by flying to a new location. Being fascinated by the scientific explanation to this phenomenon, the student started tinkering with different kinds of sensors and actuators to find a way to communicate this ecological relationship through an interactive device, and eventually created an electronic game. The player has a certain amount of time to increase the temperature sensed by a thermistor, by rubbing the game box onto another person, and find out on an LED matrix display whether a winged offspring was generated, thus granting the survival of the colony and winning the game (cf. Figure 9).

In her exploration report, student Gong Longyu recalls noticing a large number of crawling plants and how they use various strategies to hold and grow onto different kinds of surfaces. She then explored a way to understand and recreate the crawling ability of ivies experimenting with sensors and actuators and created a wearable device that can be worn as a glove to tell whether a surface is suitable for ivy’s growing or not. In her project “Ivy Touch”, a colour sensor is used to detect the texture of a surface while the output is a motor that tightens or loosens a string wrapped around the user’s hand, signalling a tight or loose hold on the tested surface (cf. Figure 10).

Figure 5: Gao Peizhong’s “Percuino”.

Figure 6: Gao Shihan's "Treelapse".

Figure 7: Zhu Ziyi's "ElectroMata412".

Figure 8: Song Yue's "Root for Thought".

by the hands-on methodology and the exploration in Nature; their design was influenced and guided by experiences and motivations that arose in harmony from elements associated with both topics.

Presenting the cause of natural phenomena as data that can be detected by an input device and their effect as a manifestation that can be reproduced with an electronic actuator allowed the students to establish a kind of empathy with the ecological system they were researching. Understanding the phenomena by means and methods of exploration is a way to see “from the perspective of the users”, being in this case agents of an ecological system. The students were able to understand and experience the ecological relationship creating a simulated representation of it, a task similar to those frequently conducted by designers in the “define” step of the Double Diamond framework (Design Council 2007).

5.1 Students' feedback

At the end of the course we circulated a questionnaire among the students to assess their experience and collect their feedback. While the totality of the students regarded the practical activities and the hands-on tutorials as useful and abundant, more than half of them asked for a larger amount of theoretical content and readings. This result is in line with the mixed top-down and bottom-up learning approach employed by the curriculum, which relies significantly on the students' ability to effectively organise their study activities and proactively seek out study materials that are specific to their project's unique direction.

We also asked the students to make a self-assessment of their skills in electronic design, fabrication and programming before their enrolment in the course, as well as after the completion of their final project. 85% rated their level before the course as below average, with the remaining 15% considering it average. After the conclusion of the course, 85% rated their level excellent, with the remaining 15% considering it above average. This positive feedback confirmed our belief that the necessary technical skills were appropriately delivered. We received positive feedback regarding the organisation of the course and the sequence of activities and challenges we programmed, with 100% of the students evaluating the structure of the course as engaging and the design brief as useful. However, we noted several written responses including insightful comments on this matter: one student felt that *“The first single exploration is a bit too limited to develop an idea”* and that *“we should start thinking about the final project earlier”*. Another student described her struggle with the tight schedule forcing her to *“pick up a research topic in a rather random way and forcing herself into deciding which design direction to take”*.

5.2 Future work

Additional explorations and development of this research are currently being planned to further validate our approach and to assess its effectiveness in a wider range of situations. Exploring the long-term impact of this curriculum on students' design practices and professional careers would provide valuable insights and we are currently tracking the trajectory of students who have experienced this integrated approach. A secondary direction we are exploring is to adapt the curriculum to become a freshman year course. We believe that introducing our approach early in the students' career would be beneficial to the development of their design practice, presenting more-than-human design as an established foundation of design education. Pursuing this direction will require a necessary simplification of the course content that should be tailored for first year's students, taking into account their abilities and the larger number of students enrolled.

6 Conclusions

The collaboration between Fablab Shanghai and the Ecology and Cultures Innovation Lab aimed to integrate technical and ecological elements in the development of a curriculum for a design studio course. Through this collaboration, we sought to foster a design culture that explores interconnectedness and extends the scope of design from human-centred to life-centred scenarios.

Based on our initial experience, we realised the importance of maintaining a continuous interconnection between technical and ecological topics throughout the course. To address this, we redesigned the Studio

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5 course, with the Fab Lab providing experiential learning activities in electronic design while promoting new interactions between citizens and Nature.

Electronic design was chosen as a technical subject due to its prevalence in contemporary products and the need for design students to understand electronic systems. Our curriculum guided students in understanding electronic components, designing circuits, fabricating prototypes, and integrating them into their design projects.

The specific brief of "Sensing Ecology" aimed to create devices that enable interactions between humans and the natural environment, fostering the acquisition of ecological knowledge. Experiential activities such as sketching components, input and output device experiments, field exploration, and rapid prototyping facilitated the integration of electronic design and ecological concepts within the methodology of a design process framework.

Reviewing the outcomes, we found that the students successfully developed their technical skills and completed the assigned tasks. By presenting the cause of natural phenomena as data to be detected and their effects as manifestations to be reproduced, students established empathy with ecological systems and were able to interpret these relationships with artificial representations. Their design decisions were influenced by their experiences and motivations, which emerged from the interplay between electronic and ecological elements.

In conclusion, our cross-disciplinary approach demonstrated the value of interlacing technical and ecological topics in design education to help students develop a research-by-doing methodology based on experiential practice and gain a deeper understanding of both the technical and ecological dimensions of their work.

Acknowledgement

The work described in this paper is supported by the National Natural Science Foundation Research Grant 2020-2022 (ID 6201101276) and the Ministry of Science and Technology of China International Cooperation grant 2022-2025 (2022YFE0197700). The experiments were made possible by the contribution of means and space from Fablab Shanghai and the Ecology and Cultures Innovation Lab of the College of Design and Innovation Tongji University.

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